

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *Language is the primary means of communication, it is difficult for you to imagine the existence and development of human society. At a time when the world is undergoing great changes, the demand for learning foreign languages is growing in our country. the study of English is very well established. At the initiative of the President, English is widely taught in all fields of education. The use of technology in the process of learning English is yielding effective results.*

Key words: *school, technology, lesson, teacher, computer, language.*

After the independence of our country, the demand for learning foreign languages has increased dramatically. The state creates ample opportunities for language learning. Today, schools have modern computers, electronic resources, Internet access. The use of information technology is possible not only at different stages of school students' lessons, but also in the usual English lessons. The introduction of computer technology in the scheme of a traditional lesson allows the teacher to make the learning process a part of his work on the computer, making the learning process more interesting, colorful, intense. The computer cannot replace it, but only fills the teachers. Involving a computer allows you to make any lesson attractive and truly modern. Completing any task allows you to increase the intensity of the lesson by using a computer and using the lesson. The use of flexible materials and operational plans help to individualize reading. It can be used at all stages of computer training: new materials, merging, repetition, knowledge management, skills and abilities can be used in the explanation. At the same time, for the child, it performs a variety of functions: teachers, tools, teaching aids, learning object, collaborative group, play environment, entertainment. It helps to introduce new pedagogical technologies, for example: data and communication, computer and multimedia technologies are closely interrelated. Implementation of information technology creates the necessary conditions for the activation of the school learning process. Computer technology helps to reveal, preserve and develop students' personal qualities. In schools, every subject in the teaching process, however, English has always used information technology (means of storing, processing and transmitting information) in their activities; Improving their perfection will help increase efficiency. Therefore, the

use of a computer as the most perfect source of information, using books, fountains, televisions, calculators, VCRs, and so on. Naturally, it leads to an improvement in the learning process. The development of computers and software has led to the simplicity of mastering their underdeveloped users, including preschoolers. In recent years, the issue of using innovative technologies in schools has been on the rise. It is not only new technical means, but also a new approach to the learning process and teaching methods, the learning process. The introduction of innovative technologies into the learning process is related to the improvement of teaching and learning methods in the process of learning foreign languages in relation to the needs of foreign languages. The main purpose of teaching in foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to learn practical skills in a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to create practical skills with language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate their activities, creativity. Collaboration, project methodology, modern pedagogical technologies using new information technologies, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of education, their individualization will help increase the level of knowledge. The communication approach is a strategy that stimulates communication and focuses on a conscious understanding of the material and ways to communicate with them. It is not very difficult for a user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A question should arise for a utility task problem or discussion, and students can not only share information but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows this approach to be distinguished from other types of activities is that students choose a language unit to express their opinions. It is better not to use the Internet in an alternative approach: its purpose is to learn a foreign language and to learn a foreign language by expanding their knowledge and experience. One of the main requirements for learning foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interactions in the so-called usual course in this interactive method. Interactivity is the organization, coordination, and complementarity of “achieving mutual goals and the outcome of speech resources”. Real language classes help in the formation of Internet skills and abilities, as well as a real interest in learning vocabulary and grammar and are therefore effective. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond adequately through foreign languages. One of the technologies that offers individual teaching is the method of these projects, which is a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity, independence. The typology of projects varies. In real practice, it has to deal with a variety of research, creative, practice-oriented, and mixed projects where there are signs of information. The work of the project is a multi-level approach to learning reading, auditing, speaking and grammar. The method of the project contributes greatly to the development of active independent thinking in students. I think project preparation teaches children to

collaborate and collaborative training raises mutual support and creative skills. At the same time, the essence of innovative education in learning English is that the involvement of almost all students in the learning process of the learning process, the use of new ped technologies increases the quality of lessons. For example, if we look at the following pad technologies.

Carousel technology. Like many innovative technologies, the carousel is borrowed. Kids do this kind of work, usually a lot. Two rings are formed will be: internal and external. Still students facing the outside of the inner ring, from the outside rotating every 30 seconds. So they have time to talk for a few minutes and try to convince the interlocutor to their right. Dialogues of a lauretic nature follow perfectly, the subject is acquaintance, nationality, conversation in a public place, and so on. The guys speak with excitement, the profession is dynamic and productive.

"Theater" technology. Something like the spectrum you participate in as an audience, experts, critics and analysts. Several students play the situation in the circle, while the rest are observed and analyzed. The appropriate mood, emotion, character of the spectators, and the task of the audience is to tell their conclusions based on what they have followed.

"Group Story" technology. It is done in two ways. In the first method, each student adds one sentence to a story that has already begun. At a certain signal (after a minute) a sheet with an unfinished story is sent in conjunction. The second method is well suited for topic development. The teacher asks questions in a certain order, each participant in the process writes an answer, no one can see it, and the neighbor helps. The movement takes place in a circle. Thus, in the end, a few surprises are obtained. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student strives to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process.

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